

copper is precipitated with 50 ml of sodium diethyl dithio carbamate³ solution (1%) and the ppt. is extracted with ethyl acetate. All copper is removed in one extraction. The ethyl acetate layer is washed and copper from the organic phase is displaced (15 ml) with silver nitrate⁴ solution. Finally, the solution is strongly diluted and made weakly basic with ammonium hydroxide and then the copper is titrated with EDTA using 10 ml of dimethyl glyoxime (1%) as an indicator from red to blue end point.

Results and Discussion

A number of brass and bronze samples are tested by this method against the electrolysis method and iodometric method and their results are indicated in Table I, which are in good agreement with one another.

TABLE I

Particulars of Samples	Iodometric Method	Cu by Electrolysis	Cu by New Method*
No. 1	70.02	70.04	70.11
No. 2	70.18	70.25	70.20
No. 3	68.48	68.56	68.50
No. 4	70.52	70.58	70.62
No. 5	67.70	67.77	67.74

* Average of 3 results.

Determination of copper by electrolysis though accurate is expensive and time consuming. On the other hand, the new method is cheaper, takes much less time and the results are reproducible as well.

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Analytical Applications of 5-Hydroxy-1,4-Naphthoquinone (Juglone)

S. S. SAWHNEY and B. M. L. BHATIA

Chemistry Department, D. A. V. (P.G.) College, Dehradun (U.P.)

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THE present note extends the application of juglone as a pH indicator¹ in the determination of glycine and hippuric acid, and deals with its use as a metal ion indicator in the estimation of nickel ion in solution complexometrically with hippuric acid as a titrant at 6.8 pH.

In the titration of hippuric acid (N/50 and N/100) with NaOH (N/46.30 and N/96), juglone with pH range 7.8-9.9 and colour change: yellow to violet, was found more suitable than phenolphthalein, methyl-red and lapachol². Standard deviation as low as 0.05 could be achieved in the case of juglone. Relative errors in different case are:

Indicator	Relative Error (%)	
	Analyte : Titration :	N/50 N/100
Juglone	0.21	0.41
Phenolphthalein	0.75	2.50
Methyl-red	3.45	4.58
Lapachol	2.15	5.41

In the estimation of glycine, juglone as a pH indicator in the place of phenolphthalein, employing sorenson formula in titration method, with relative error as 0.02% is quantitative in nature. Standard deviation as low as 0.02 could be achieved.

Juglone as Metal Ion Indicator :

Nickel-juglone complex with metal ligand molar ratio of 1 : 2 is less stable than nickel-hippuric acid complex having metal to ligand combining ratio as 1 : 2. With progressive complexation of nickel ion by hippuric acid at 6.8 pH, nickel ion is ultimately displaced from nickel-juglone complex (red) to leave free juglone (yellow). Juglone exhibits acid-base behaviour in the pH range 7.8-9.9 in which it exhibits violet colour. It is yellow below 7.8 pH. Nickel forms red complex³ with juglone at 6.8 pH.

Under the experimental conditions, juglone as a metal ion indicator with relative error as 0.6% appears to be suitable in the estimation of nickel ion complexometrically. E.D.T.A. titration yielded far better results. Standard deviation as low as 0.3 could be achieved. Ions like Co²⁺, Cu²⁺, Mn²⁺, Al³⁺, Fe³⁺, interfered.

Procedure :

Dilute 5 ml (0.1 M) nickel ion solution to 10 ml with distilled water. Add 4 ml of buffer solution (6.8 pH) and 1 ml (0.02M) indicator. Titrate with (0.02M) hippuric acid until colour change from red to yellow. Blank was also run for better results.

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Direct Estimation of Zinc in Complex Materials

DHARAM PRAKASH, CHANDRA SHEKHAR
and
SURESH CHANDRA

Chemical Laboratory, Directorate of Geology and Mining,
2 Way Road, Lucknow

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ZINC belongs to the more common trace elements. Its average concentration in the lithosphere is in the order of 60-70 p.p.m. It mostly occurs as the sulfide, sphalerite, ZnS, but the carbonate smithsonite ZnCO₃ and the silicate willemite Zn₂(SiO₄) are also common zinc minerals. The occurrence of zinc in silicate rocks was examined by Sandell and Goldich who found that the amounts of zinc present in rocks of the plutonic and volcanic series could be related to the sum of the magnesium and ferrous iron, and also to the manganese content. Rader has also shown that the zinc content of basaltic rocks can be related to the total iron content. In metallurgical products particularly in the non-ferrous field zinc is often encountered and its analysis called for, except where it is one of the principal constituents, as in brass (Zn, Cu) German Silver (Zn, Cu, Ni) and in die casting alloys (Zn, Cu, Al) where it is commonly reported by difference. Granulated zinc is a necessary substance in the chemical laboratory. Its resistance to rusting makes zinc valuable as a protective coating on iron surfaces (galvanized iron). Considerable quantities of zinc are used as anodes in electrical batteries. The ZnO is used as a pigment and chemical in rubber goods, including automobile tyres and extensively as a paint pigment. It is used in glazes, in enamels, as an ointment, as dusting powder etc. The chloride is used as a preservative of wood. The sulfide is a valuable white pigment, with barium sulphate it forms lithopone. Recently zinc has been shown to be necessary to the growth

of plants, certain chemical glasswares contain from 3-11% zinc. Zinc determination should not be made in these wares.

The quantitative estimation of zinc in a complex material, where it is associated with, Cu, Pb, Al, Fe, Mg, Ca, Cd etc. is a tedious process. The gravimetric methods are quite lengthy, because the separation of each group is required before reaching the IV group (Zn, Ni, Co, etc. comes in fourth group) and also during the precipitation of zinc with diammonium hydrogen phosphate magnesium interferes. In the volumetric analysis zinc can be titrated with EDTA using Eriochrome Black T at pH 10 but in the presence of Mg this method proved futile.

Zinc at pH 6 forms coloured complex with xylenol orange (red complex). When it is titrated with standard EDTA, the colour change at the equivalence point is from red to yellow. This method has successfully been applied for the estimation of zinc present in rock and minerals where it is generally associated with several elements viz. Cu, Pb, Al, Fe, Mg, Ca and Cd etc.

In the proposed method Pb has been removed as PbSO₄ and filtered off alongwith silica. Iron has also been removed as iron-hydroxide by precipitating it with NaOH, copper and aluminium is complexed with sodium thiosulphate and sodium fluoride respectively and zinc is titrated directly with standard 0.01M EDTA at pH 6 (which was maintained using hexamine) using 0.5% xylenol orange as indicator. The colour change at the end point is from red to yellow. Magnesium and calcium do not interfere at pH 6.

Reagents :

1-EDTA : 0.01M—3.7225 gms of EDTA was weighed and dissolved in one litre of distilled water.

2-Sodium thiosulphate—10% soln. 10 gms of sodium thiosulphate was dissolved in 100 ml distilled water.

3-Sodium fluoride 5% solution—5 gms sodium fluoride was dissolved in 100 ml distilled water.

4-Hexamine—It is used as buffer to maintain pH 6.

5-Xylenol orange 0.5% (0.5 gms) of the reagent was weighed, dissolved in little alcohol and was made upto 100 ml by distilled water.

Experimental

Several samples of zinc were weighed. The samples were decomposed by 1 : 2 HNO₃ and